

mm) at 2.5 and 3.0 lb pressure. The bursting of grains upon cooking decreased and the degree of whiteness of polished grain increased with increased milling pressure. The highest protein content in milled rice (9.2%) and oil

content in bran (20.95%) were recorded at the lowest pressure, whereas the lowest values were recorded at the maximum pressure. The water absorption ratio and the volume expansion ratio were maximum at the intermediate milling

pressures of 2.0 and 2.5 lb.

The results indicate that no single milling pressure optimizes all of the desirable grain quality characteristics. Milling pressures of 2.5-3.0 lb appear to be suitable for Basmati 385. ■

Changes in milled rice cooking quality after storage as rough or milled rice

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We compared the cooking quality of fine-grain strain 4048 after storage as either milled or rough rice. Half of a sample was milled; the other half was left rough. The samples were stored in separate cloth

bags for 12 mo during 1990-91 at ambient temperatures of 16-38 °C in the RRI Rice Technology Laboratory.

We milled a portion from the stored rough rice sample every month. Cooking quality tests were performed on both the freshly milled rice sample (from stored rough rice) and the stored milled rice. To ensure a uniform degree of milling, all samples were polished using the same pressure and time period.

Values for cooked grain length and elongation ratio were higher for grain

stored as milled rice than for grain stored as rough rice (see table). The bursting of cooked grain, volume expansion ratio, water absorption ratio, and losses of solids from rice during cooking (gruel) were higher for grain stored as rough rice than for that stored as milled rice.

Rice stored as milled grain improved in cooking quality as it aged and had greater elongation, less bursting, and less loss of solids than rice stored as rough grain. ■

Cooking quality of rice stored as milled or rough rice. RRI, Kala Shah Kaku, Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan, 1990-91.

Cooking characteristic of milled rice	Freshly harvested ^a	Stored for												Mean ^b	CV (%)	LSD value	
		2 mo		4 mo		6 mo		8 mo		10 mo		12 mo					
		Rough	Milled	Rough	Milled	Rough	Milled	Rough	Milled	Rough	Milled	Rough	Milled				
Cooked grain length (mm)	14.10	14.30	14.40	14.70	14.90	14.90	15.10	15.20	15.40	15.50	15.60	15.70	15.80	14.91	b15.01 a	0.4	0.07
Elongation ratio	1.89	1.91	1.93	1.97	1.99	1.99	2.02	2.03	2.06	2.07	2.09	2.10	2.11	1.99	b 2.01 a	0.4	0.01
Bursting of grain upon cooking (%)	8.0	7.1	6.7	6.0	5.2	5.7	4.0	5.5	3.1	5.2	2.6	5.0	2.0	6.1	a 4.5 b	15.7	1.08
Volume expansion ratio upon soaking	1.25	1.26	1.26	1.27	1.27	1.28	1.27	1.28	1.28	1.29	1.28	1.30	1.28	1.28	a 1.27 b	0.4	0.004
Volume expansion ratio upon cooking	2.71	2.90	2.87	3.15	3.04	3.25	3.20	3.33	3.29	3.44	3.32	3.57	3.38	3.19	a 3.12 b	1.5	0.06
Water absorption ratio upon soaking	1.18	1.19	1.18	1.19	1.19	1.21	1.20	1.21	1.20	1.22	1.21	1.23	1.21	1.20	a 1.19 b	0.4	0.004
Water absorption ratio upon cooking	2.20	2.28	2.26	2.33	2.30	2.40	2.35	2.55	2.49	2.63	2.57	2.72	2.65	2.44	a 2.40 b	0.7	0.004
Loss of solids in washing water (%)	1.3	1.0	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.7	0.6	0.6	0.4	0.6	0.3	0.5	0.3	0.8	a 0.7 b	8.6	0.08
Loss of solids in gruel (%)	6.8	6.1	5.8	5.4	4.8	4.3	3.9	4.0	3.7	3.9	3.4	3.7	3.3	4.9	4.6	2.5	0.16

^aValues for rough and milled rice were the same. ^bMeans in a row followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.